

Starting strong: development and biomechanics of the seedling-host interaction in European mistletoe (*Viscum album*)

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Supplement Information and Figures

Detailed documentation of mistletoe germination

Of the 72 seeds sown, 60 germinated (83.3%), with the remaining 12 seeds desiccating or no longer attached to the branch (first developmental stage). The influence of H₂O₂-treatment of the seeds had a marked influence on the rate of developmental stages reached (germination rate with treatment 97.2% and without treatment 69.4%) and reduced the time to germination from an average of 7 weeks (untreated) to 4 weeks. The influence on the seed placement on top (germination rate 91.4%) or below (germination rate 75.0%) the host branch revealed another influencing factor. The seeds on the apple trees germinated at a rate of 87.5%, while those on the quince trees germinated at a rate of 78.1%. Among the germinated seedlings, 34 samples had one embryo (56.7%), 22 had two germinating embryos (36.7%) and 4 samples had three germinating embryos (6.6%). In samples with more than one embryo, the developmental stage of the first embryo was used for further evaluation. During seedling development, in addition to seed detachment from the branch, losses occurred due to death of single or all hypocotyls or unsuccessful penetration of the host branch. Samples collected for microtomographic analysis were not included in the analysis from this point forward, and the respective rates of reaching the next stage were adjusted accordingly.

75.0% of all seedlings made contact with the host tree (second developmental stage) and 72.2% developed a holdfast structure (third developmental stage). For both stages, there was little difference between the host trees, with a contact rate of 77.5% for seedlings on the apple trees and 71.9% on the quince, and a holdfast formation rate of 72.5% on apple trees and 71.9% on quince. The duration of these two stages was independent of the host tree, the treatment of the seeds and their placement at two to three weeks each. A striking difference was observed in the number of seedlings in which the host showed a hypertrophic response (fourth developmental stage), which occurred in 51.4% of the seedlings on the apple trees and in none of the seedlings on the quince. Overall, the rate of host hypertrophy was 26.9%. The influence of H₂O₂-treatment on the success rate of seedlings decreased continuously through the stages of host contact (86.1% treated vs. 63.9% untreated), holdfast formation (83.3% treated vs. 61.1% untreated), and host hypertrophy response (27.3% treated vs. 26.5%

untreated). The effect of placement on the host branch was reversed during the developmental steps: For host contact (83.3% above to 66.7% below) and holdfast formation (77.8% above to 66.7% below), the relative values of upper attachment were higher, while a hypertrophic response of the host was more frequent with the seeds attached below (23.5% above to 30.3% below). A detailed overview on durations of the single stages can be found in Fig. S1 and the course of the germination rates, along with the temperature conditions during seedling development, is presented in Fig. S2. In both figures, the data are summarised for all samples, but also subdivided by host tree, berry treatment and berry placement.

Supplement Figure S1: Mean duration of germination stages for all samples analysed and subdivided according to the treatment type, the placement on host branch and the host tree. All samples that fully reached the stage were included in the calculation of durations.

Supplement Figure S2: Development of seeds sown from January to September 2023 at 24 different observation times as relative proportions of the entire sampling. The data include all samples from both *Viscum* berry sowing dates (dashed lines) on the three host trees (one quince and two apples). The temperature profile during the observation period is represented by the mean and maximum temperatures recorded by the weather station near the experimental site.

Lugol's solution treatment for microtomographic scans

To compare the influence of Lugol's solution on the CT recordings, we scanned the 21-week-old sample with and without the contrast agent. Figure S3 depicts the variations in the resulting brightness, caused by differences in tissue density, and thus the improved differentiation of tissues within an organism, but also between the two species. In mistletoe tissues, Lugol's solution facilitates differentiation between the lighter hypocotyl and the darker seed (Figure S3A&C). In the host plant, the contrast between the darker pith, the lighter xylem, and the darker bark becomes apparent, allowing a more accurate identification of the cambium layer

(Figure S3B&D). In addition, the annual ring and the phloem in the bark are easier to distinguish. The effect of the Lugol's solution is particularly noticeable at the interface between the host and the light-coloured penetration organ of the mistletoe (Figure S3C&D). However, certain scan details vanish when contrasting with Lugol's solution, such as the host cortex structure becoming less distinguishable and the bright dots within the mistletoe hypocotyl disappearing due to denser mistletoe tissue after contrasting.

Supplement Figure S3: Comparison of microCT images of a 21-week-old mistletoe seedling and its host branch. The sample was scanned after FAA fixation (**A,B**) and then again after immersion in Lugol's solution as contrast solution (**C,D**). Tangential (**A&C**) and transverse (**B&D**) host branch section of the mistletoe seed, seedling and its host. Penetration peg (pp), adhesive disc/holdfast (hf), hypocotyl (hy), mistletoe seed (s), host bud (hb), bark (b), cambium (c), xylem (x) and pith (m) are visible.